

Environmental Scan Summary

The following provides an overview of neighbourhood assets and potential barriers/gaps for older adults. The features were identified through a structured assessment in July 2023. As such, this summary should be viewed as an overview of key features observed rather than an exhaustive list.

Corman is a mostly residential neighbourhood located in east Hamilton. Single detached homes are the main housing type, but large apartment buildings, small apartment buildings, and townhouses are also present. The properties here tend to be between 40-60 years old, with many of them being multi-car homes. Services, retail stores, housing, and health/social centers are predominantly located at perimeter of the neighbourhood.

Most people were driving, travelling by transit can be difficult in Corman as a result of the low service level. Nonetheless, there are a few bus lines passing through the neighbourhood, and bus stops are typically nearby. This neighbourhood is reasonably quiet, as noise from the streets and other parts of the city does not appear to be an issue.

Corman is home to a considerable number of older adults, and its population exhibits diversity, evident in the range of multicultural food options available at the local Freshco grocery store, accompanied by advertisements in multiple languages. However, community centers and places of worship do not necessarily reflect this diversity, aside from a gospel hall and a Serbian Orthodox Temple.

The neighbourhood offers two parks, Glendale Park and Sisters of St. Joseph Park, providing accessible public green spaces for residents to enjoy. While biking may sometimes be challenging due to limited cycling infrastructure, most of these parks are easily reachable from various locations within Corman. Health services in the area include Vitality Health and Wellness Clinic, Arbour Creek Care Centre, Red Hill Orthodontics, Pharmasave, and a MedRehab Clinic. However, mental health facilities were not observed directly within the neighborhood. The Hamilton Police Department has a branch situated in the adjacent neighborhood.

Corman's strength lies in its ethnic diversity and the affordability of stores. Multiple Dollar Stores, with some plazas having two, offer residents a diverse array of shopping options at varying price points.

Map of services identified in Corman

Index of services in Corman

Index Number	Description
Education	
1	Glendale Secondary School
Fitness/Recreation	
2	Aroma Day Spa
3	Good Life Fitness
Food Sources	
4	Etno Bar + Grill
5	Euro Treats
6	No Frills*
7	FreshCo*
8	Kelsey's Original Roadhouse
9	McDonald's
10	Pizza Hut
11	Starsky Fine Foods*
	*Grocery and/or whole food stores
Health/Social Services	
12	Arbour Creek Care Centre
13	Dr Harding L Office
14	MedRehab Clinic Group
15	Pharmasave Queenston Place Pharmacy
16	Red Hill Orthodontics
17	Vitality Health and Wellness Clinic

Housing

- 18 [Albion Court Apartments](#)
- 19 [Birchwood Apartments](#)
- 20 [Centennial Court Apartments](#)
- 21 [Eldorado Apartments](#)
- 22 [King Manor Apartments](#)
- 23 Glen Garden Apartments

Parks

- 24 Glendale Park
- 25 Sisters of St. Joseph Park

Religious Centres

- 26 [Nash Road Gospel Hall](#)
- 27 [St. Nicholas Serbian Orthodox Cathedral](#)

Retail

- 28 [Arze Auto](#)
- 29 [Canadian Tire](#)
- 30 [Dollar Tree](#)
- 31 [Dollarama](#)

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Binkley C. & Ling E. On behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team (2023). Environmental scan: Corman. URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects-results/>

CT Highlights

Population
= 3,476

Number of Homes
= 1,692

Population Density
= 3,683/Km²

5-year Population change = 2.3%

Age Distribution by Gender

\$36,440
Average Income (after tax)

17.3%
Unemployment Rate

Citizenship & Immigrant Population

Canadian Citizens

Immigrants Recent Immigrants

Language Spoken at Home

English | 76.1%
 Non-official Languages | 19.4%

Highest Certificate, Diploma or Degree

- 16% No certificate, diploma or degree
- 33% Secondary (high) school diploma or equivalency
- 51% Postsecondary certificate, diploma or degree

Neighbourhood Homes

Average monthly shelter costs

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Data Source Statistics Canada. 20215370026.01 [Census tract].
www.statcan.gc.ca

Siddiqui, S., Orr, E., Ganann., R. On behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team. (2023).
 Infographic: Neighbourhood Profile
 URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects/results/>